

FIGURE 6-1
 Physical and Chemical Conceptual Site Model
 Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
 Brooklyn, New York

Known or potential sources of contamination:

Primary

Secondary

CSO - combined sewer overflow
 NAPL - non-aqueous phase liquid

FIGURE 6-2a
 Conceptual Site Model - Known or Potential Sources of Contamination
 Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
 Brooklyn, New York

Nature and extent of contamination

BTEX - benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene, and xylenes
 PAH - polynuclear aromatic hydrocarbon
 PCB - polychlorinated biphenyl
 NAPL - non-aqueous phase liquid

FIGURE 6-2b
 Conceptual Site Model – Nature and Extent of Contamination
 Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
 Brooklyn, New York

Contaminant Fate and Transport Mechanisms

FIGURE 6-2c
 Conceptual Site Model – Contaminant Fate and Transport Mechanisms
 Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
 Brooklyn, New York

BTEX, total PCBs, and total DDT are not shown because of low detection frequency in surface sediment.

BTEX – benzene, ethylbenzene, toluene, and xylenes
 PAH – polynuclear aromatic hydrocarbon

FIGURE 6-3
 Concentration Gradients in Surface Sediment
 Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
 Brooklyn, New York

FIGURE 6-4

Contaminant Concentration Gradients in Soft Sediment and Native Sediment
 Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
 Brooklyn, New York

BTEX – benzene, ethylbenzene, toluene, and xylenes
 PAH – polynuclear aromatic hydrocarbon
 PCB – polychlorinated biphenyl
 DDT - dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane

Legend

- Lead 210
- - - Cesium 137

Activity in disintegrations per minute per gram (dpm/g)

FIGURE 6-5a
 Radioisotope Profiles for Cores Collected
 North of 3rd Street
 Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
 Brooklyn, New York

Core data from GEI (2007)

Legend

- Lead 210
- - - Cesium 137

Activity in disintegrations per minute per gram (dpm/g)

FIGURE 6-5b

Radioisotope Profiles for Cores Collected South of 3rd Street
Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
Brooklyn, New York

Core data from GEI (2007)